

Configuration of the Hydroxyl Groups in Cassaidine

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Cassaidine is an alkaloid isolated from the bark of *Erythrophleum guineense* G. Don (Ruzicka and Dalma, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, **23**, 753). Acid hydrolysis of cassaidine affords *NN*-dimethylaminoethanol and a diterpene acid, cassaidic acid, which contains two hydroxyl groups. Mild oxidation with chromic acid converts this acid to diketocassenic acid, which has also been obtained by the oxidation of cassaic acid, a closely related diterpene acid containing the same carbon skeleton as cassaidic acid. This acid contains one hydroxyl group and a keto group (Dalma, *ibid.*, 1939, **22**, 1947; Faltis and Holzinger, *Ber.*, 1939, **72**, 1443).

The structure and configuration of cassaic acid has been shown to be (I) by Turner *et al.* (*Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, **2**, 7). Engel (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1959, **42**, 1127) has independently assigned a 3β -equatorial configuration to the hydroxyl group in cassaic acid. Evidence presented in this communication indicates that both hydroxyl groups in cassaidine(II) possess β -equatorial orientation.

Cassaic acid was reduced with sodium borohydride to cassaidic acid, m. p. 275°, $[\alpha]_D -102^\circ$ ($c=1$), λ_{max} 219 m μ , $\log \epsilon$ 4.22 (ethanol), infrared bands (in nujol mull) at 3500, 1692, 1645 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 71.25; H, 9.79. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{32}O_4$: C, 71.39; H, 9.59%). Treatment of cassaidic acid with ethereal diazomethane furnished methyl cassaidate, m. p. 162-63° (lit. m. p. 162-63°), $[\alpha]_D -104^\circ$, λ_{max} 223 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.22 (ethanol), infrared bands ($CHCl_3$ solution), 1700, 1645 cm^{-1} . Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of methyl cassaidate furnished an unsaturated triol (III), m. p. 218-20°, $[\alpha]_D -87^\circ$. (Found: C, 74.89; H, 10.68. $C_{20}H_{34}O_3$ requires C, 74.49; H, 10.63%). This compound did not exhibit any significant ultraviolet absorption above 210 m μ . Infrared bands (in KBr-disc) at 3400, 3300, 1010, 1015 (hydroxyls) 1665 cm^{-1} ($>C=CH-$). On microhydrogenation over 10% Pd/C catalyst, one mole of hydrogen was absorbed. In chloroform-methanol (1:1) solution the triol consumed one mole of perbenzoic acid in 24 hrs. at 4°.

On reduction of methyl cassate under similar conditions, the same *triol* (III) was obtained in about 80% yield. The results of these reduction experiments prove that both hydroxyl groups in cassaidic acid and consequently in cassaidine have the β -equatorial configuration.

The author expresses sincere thanks to Dr. D. W. Mathieson for his interest in this work which was carried out in the School of Pharmacy, London, England.

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Received April 25, 1961.